

Sample 13a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0614
	{Si}	40.5
	{Fe}	8.8
	{Cl}	7.9
	{Al, Si}	5.8
	{S, Ca}	5.0
	{Ca}	4.6
	{Cl}	4.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.9
	{Si, Cl}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.4
	{Na, Si}	1.3
	{Si, Fe}	1.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	1.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	1.0
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Ca}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Al, Si, K}	0.5
	{Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Zn-LA1}	0.4
	{Al}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.3
	{S}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, S, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Al, Cl}	0.2
	{Mg, Cl}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	2.8
Pellet	1.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	1.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	3.5
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	1.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.6
Carbon rich - other	13.1
Cement or BOF converter	1.8
Cement	1.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	2.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	37.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	18.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.3
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.3
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	6.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	5.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.2
Site - flux / slag	1.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	1.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.5
Site - carbon-rich other	1.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	13.1
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.8
Urban	3.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.1
Natural mineral background	37.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	18.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 13b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.1145
	{Si}	41.0
	{Fe}	11.5
	{Al, Si}	6.9
	{Cl}	6.3
	{S, Ca}	5.6
	{Ca}	4.5
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.4
	{Cl}	2.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.0
	{Si, Fe}	1.8
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.1
	{Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	1.0
	{Na, Si}	0.8
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Al, Si, K}	0.6
	{Zn-LA1}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Al}	0.4
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, S, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.9
Pellet	3.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	5.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.4
BOF converter slag	0.5
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.1
Desulph slag	0.6
Ca-aluminate slag	0.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.7
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.7
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	4.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.3
Carbon rich - other	11.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.0
Cement	1.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	2.4
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.2
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	40.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	19.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.3
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	10.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.4
Site - slag	3.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	1.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.7
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.8
Site - carbon-rich other	1.3
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	11.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.0
Urban	3.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	40.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	19.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.1
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.1

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 13c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0031
	{Si}	47.1
	{Fe}	8.6
	{Cl}	7.9
	{S, Ca}	5.5
	{Al, Si}	4.6
	{Ca}	3.9
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.6
	{Cl}	2.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.0
	{Si, Fe}	1.5
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.1
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.1
	{Si, Cl}	1.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.9
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Al, Si, K}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Zn-LA1}	0.3
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, S, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Cl, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	3.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.7
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.6
Desulph slag	2.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.0
Carbon rich - other	12.2
Cement or BOF converter	0.8
Cement	0.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	2.4
Ti-rich paint	0.4
Ba-sulphate bearing	1.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	40.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	16.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.3
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	6.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	5.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.8
Site - carbon-rich other	3.0
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	12.2
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.8
Urban	4.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	40.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	16.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels